

PSYCHOLOGICAL CARE WITH MENTAL PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

this article describes how a person with serious mental instability reacts to statements, behavior of himself and his interlocutor he won't have the ability to analyze. The thought "I'm right, people around me don't understand" does not leave them. Therefore, be careful when dealing with people with mental imbalance is required.

It is known that the physical and financial condition of people always causes concern, namely, that their tomorrow is directly worried about the day, thinks about their loved ones, worries about them. Regulatory and legal discussions on the portal of documents "registration of persons with mental disorders and dynamic monitoring draft order of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation" The approval of the Procedure Instructions has been done. According to the instructions, dispensary supervision is carried out at the site of medical and preventive institutions by psychiatrists.

Dispensary observation of severe stable or often severe disorders of chronic and prolonged mental state with manifestations of standing anguish can be established regardless of the consent of the victim, as well as his legal representative. Those around such patients should provide them with moral support. If they do, their mood will also be calm. The term mental illness refers to disorders of the nervous system that arise as a result of division, leading to behavior that sharply goes beyond the norms established in society the disease is understandable. Mental illness is often associated with both the patient's behavior itself and it is also characterized by danger to humans.

Not only acute cases, but also acute and chronic concomitant mental disorders, even cases of remission, are observed by the patient with unexpected behavioral actions and require urgent care. Mental illnesses, mood disorders, psychoses are diseases caused by disorders of brain activity : from functional changes in mental functioning to its complete violation of circumstances. As noted above, mental disorders largely depend on the behavior of the patient. Many patients experience mental stress and depression when they notice that they have a certain disease. they also fall into a trap. As an example, OK, let's not go into the distant past, How mentally ill people were when COVID-19 infection was first detected in our country on March 15, 2020 Let's remember one drawback! At that time, quarantine was declared, everyone against self -infection was preparing to fight, they stayed away from their

loved ones: there were even those who could not see their parents for months. If we talk about the fact that this infection has become a scourge of the XXI century in the history of mankind, then scientists believe that it was also an antivirus. medical treatment. But until then, how many people have become victims of the virus. Some believe that the virus if an infected person died from a concomitant disease, some cannot get infected with the virus because of their panic, he died of fear. People have lost their composure!

The famous scientist – to the whole world Abu Ali ibn Sina, the famous author of al-Qain fit-Tib, said: "calmness is half of health, and patience is healing." In fact, without patience, no results are achievable. Whether a person has any bottlenecks, without succumbing to individual negative emotions, he needs healing-he must be able to find a way to heal. Because this pain is also given by the creator, his life is a test on the trails. Our people:"the healing that causes him pain will definitely give"- they say. This idea has been confirmed many times. But this means that he gives his healing in this way, does not mean. A person should look for measures to overcome the disease using his mind and thinking. Nothing can be done without movement. A running river is a sitting mat!

In mental illness, the patient cannot perceive the event correctly, in this respect, mental illness is intrinsically different from diseases. The causes of mental illness are diverse, among them the hereditary factor (nyel) is the main one that occupies a place. Mas, oligophrenia, psychopathy, manic-depressive psychosis, epilepsy and schizophrenia human genealogy plays an important role in its origin. Infectious diseases, traumatic brain injuries, intoxication, mental suffering can also be the cause of the occurrence and exacerbation of mental illnesses. maybe. Damage to the fetus due to illness or injury to the mother during pregnancy leads to a lag in the child's mental development, epilepsy and other mental changes.

Chronic alcoholism and drug addiction can also gradually lead a person to mental illness. In addition to the factors causing the disease, the person himself is involved in the occurrence of mental illness. characteristic features, diseases that he had previously suffered (mas, traumatic brain injury, alcohol poisoning, diseases of internal organs, the presence of mental illness in offspring, etc.) are also important.

How to treat the mentally ill? October 10 is World Mental Health Day. 1948

The World Health Organization has established the World Federation of Psychological Health for the Prevention of psychological and emotional diseases among the world's population engaged in care. World Mental Health Day, which has been held since 1992, also informs society about psychological diseases, their origin and prevention strive for perfection.

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